

Retrieving and broadcasting near-real-time biophysical parameters from MODIS and SEVIRI receiving stations at the global change unit of the University of Valencia

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We present here the automatic processing chains implemented at the Global Change Unit of the University of Valencia. These allow for a near-real-time retrieval of various biophysical parameters from both Sun-synchronous TERRA/AQUA Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and geostationary Meteosat Second Generation Spinning Enhanced Visible and Infrared Imager (MSG SEVIRI) sensors. Retrieved parameters, namely sea and land surface temperatures (SST and LST, respectively), normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), and vegetation condition index (VCI), are similar for both sensors, and specific approaches have been developed and implemented for near-real-time parameter retrievals: <2 hours for MODIS and <5 min for MSG SEVIRI. Bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) correction is still required to be implemented in both processing chains, while more advanced parameters are already retrieved (hot spot detection and MSG SEVIRI phenology), in good agreement with independent ground observations. Validation of the retrieved products is underway and the above-mentioned products are available for downloading at <http://ceosspain.lpi.uv.es>.

1. Introduction

With an ever increasing number of satellites orbiting our planet, the amount of data available for Earth observation is rapidly growing. However, due to the amount of data processed, official repositories for remotely sensed biophysical products do not usually provide a near-real-time access to these data.

Within the framework of the Spanish CEOS-SPAIN project, a processing and broadcasting scheme has been developed and implemented at the Global Change Unit of the University of Valencia, taking advantage of the receiving Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and Meteosat Second Generation Spinning Enhanced Visible and Infrared Imager (MSG SEVIRI) stations. The processing scheme has been designed with the goal of near-real-time processing of the data, estimating biophysical parameters as straightforwardly as possible. The selected parameters for estimation are the following: sea and land surface temperatures (SST and LST, respectively), for which the total amount of water vapour (WV) and emissivities are needed; normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI); and vegetation condition index (VCI). However, different corrections are needed for accurate retrieval of these parameters, such as atmospheric correction and bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) correction for visible bands.

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This article presents in detail the data received by the MODIS and MSG SEVIRI stations located at the Global Change Unit, as well as the processing chain for MODIS and MSG SEVIRI data. Finally, a few applications of these data are presented.

2. Data

Two different streams of data are received at the Global Change Unit, from MSG SEVIRI and MODIS platforms. SEVIRI data are provided by the MSG geostationary platform, at 3 km resolution at nadir, with an image every 15 min, amounting to 21 GB/day before processing. This sensor acquires 11 bands, of which two are located in the visible and near-infrared wavelengths (Vis06 and Vis08), two located in the middle infrared wavelengths (Ir016 and Ir039), and seven located in the 6–14 μm thermal infrared spectral region (Wv062, Wv073, Ir087, Ir097, Ir108, Ir120, and Ir134), where the number indicates the central wavelength (to be multiplied by 100 nm).

MODIS data are Sun-synchronous, with around three overpasses during the day and three during the night, amounting to 4 GB/day before processing. The MODIS instrument provides data in 36 spectral bands ranging in wavelength from 0.4 to 14.4 μm . Two bands are imaged at a nominal resolution of 250 m at nadir (visible and near-infrared wavelengths), with five bands at 500 m (visible to middle infrared) and the remaining 29 at 1 km (middle to thermal infrared).

MODIS data consist of the satellite overpasses within reach of the antenna located at the University of Valencia, overpasses which cover most of Western Europe, while SEVIRI data consist of the entire hemisphere centred on the (0,0) latitude and longitude point. [Figure 1](#) presents quicklooks for both MODIS and SEVIRI single acquisitions. MODIS quicklook ([Figure 1\(a\)](#)) is a Red–Green–Blue (RGB) composite, with bands 1, 4, and 3 coded as R, G, and B, respectively, for daytime acquisitions, while for night-time acquisitions a greyscale image of thermal band 31 is used (not shown). As a result, vegetation appears in MODIS quicklook as green, clouds as white, and sand as yellow. SEVIRI quicklook ([Figure 1\(b\)](#)) is also an RGB composite, with bands IR108, Vis06, and Vis08 coded as R, G, and B, respectively. Therefore, high-temperature areas appear as red, vegetation as green, and clouds as light blue.

Each data stream is received respectively on a dedicated computer and then processed by another dedicated computer, finally to be uploaded to a common server. A web of control routines between computers allows for the early detection of any reception, processing, or archiving failures.

3. MODIS processing

Both MODIS and MSG SEVIRI streams of data are processed linearly following a similar scheme (see [Table 1](#)). The selected algorithms for MODIS processing were chosen from a literature review and are based on standard procedures, such as contextual fire detection (Mod14; [Giglio et al. 2003](#)); Mod35 cloud screening ([Ackerman et al. 2010](#)); Simplified Method for Atmospheric Correction (SMAC; [Rahman and Dedieu 1994](#)), completed using specific methods described briefly below. Characteristics (resolution, average sample size, etc.) of each of the products described hereafter are presented in [Table 2](#).

Figure 1. MODIS (a) and SEVIRI (b) quicklooks of received data at the Global Change Unit of the University of Valencia. MODIS quicklook is a Red–Green–Blue (RGB) composite with bands 1, 4, and 3, while SEVIRI RGB quicklook uses bands IR108, Vis06, and Vis08. See text for details.

Table 1. Description of the processing chain and products retrieved from both MODIS and MSG SEVIRI data streams. Products in bold type are available for download from CEOS-SPAIN online geo-portal: <http://ceosspain.lpi.uv.es>.

Processing step	MODIS	MSG SEVIRI
Data unpacking and calibrating	Yes	Yes
Geolocation	Yes	No
Hot spot detection	Mod14 (Giglio et al. 2003)	Calle, Casanova, and Romo (2006)
Cloud detection	Mod35 (Ackerman et al. 2010)	No
Water vapour	Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li (2003)	Julien et al. (2015)
Atmospheric correction	SMAC (Rahman and Dedieu 1994)	SMAC (Rahman and Dedieu 1994)
BRDF correction	Not yet	Not yet
Sea surface temperature	El Kharraz (2004)	Romaguera, Sobrino, and Olesen (2006)
NDVI	Tucker (1979)	Tucker (1979)
Vegetation condition index	Kogan (1995)	Kogan (1995)
Land surface emissivity	Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li (2003)	Romaguera (2004)
Land surface temperature	Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li (2003)	Atitar and Sobrino (2009)
Quicklooks	Yes	Yes
Upload to webpage	Yes	Yes
Compression	Yes	Yes
Upload to server	Yes	Yes

3.1. Preprocessing

The MODIS reception station located at the Global Change Unit of the University of Valencia is equipped with Scanex software, which allows the acquisition and decoding of the image into level 0 data. Indeed, this software package carries out geolocation, calibration (to radiances), and land-, cloud-, and fire-mask building, as stand-alone executable modules from console commands. To that end, two ancillary files must be downloaded regularly from <ftp://oceans.gsfc.nasa.gov/COMMON>, namely 'utcpole.dat' and 'leapsec.dat'. Therefore, the executable Scanex modules allow for the generation of level 2 products.

However, the MODIS instrument, due to its detector geometry, does not acquire data with exactly identical gain for each detector line, resulting in stripes in the acquired data. To correct this effect, the method presented by Horn and Woodham (1979) is applied. This method (also called cumulative histogram matching) consists of building a specific histogram for each line of detectors for each MODIS acquisition band, which are then intercalibrated and matched to the corresponding band histogram.

Atmospheric correction then has to be implemented only during the daytime for bands 1–7. To that end, the SMAC software (Rahman and Dedieu 1994) was selected. This software is available as both Interactive Data Language (IDL) function and executable. This programme runs on a pixel-by-pixel basis and needs additional information such as (standard values in parentheses): atmosphere type (continental), atmospheric pressure (1013 hPa), aerosol optical thickness (0.05), and ozone concentration (0.33 atm.cm). Additionally, the WV product is needed as an input for the SMAC software. Therefore, the WV product is calculated prior to atmospheric correction.

In regard to thermal channels, the estimation of brightness temperature is required, by inversion of Planck's law:

$$T_i = \frac{c_2 / \lambda_{\text{eff}}}{\ln\left(\frac{c_1}{\lambda_{\text{eff}}^5 B(T_i)} + 1\right)}, \quad (1)$$

where T_i is the brightness temperature in each thermal band, $c_1 = 1.1491047 \times 10^8 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^4$, $c_2 = 1.4387752 \times 10^4 \text{ K } \mu\text{m}$, $B(T_i)$ is the at-sensor radiance expressed in $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, and λ_{eff} is the effective wavelength (in μm) for each MODIS band i .

3.2. Near-real-time products

3.2.1. Normalized difference vegetation index

NDVI is estimated as (Tucker 1979)

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\rho_2 - \rho_1}{\rho_2 + \rho_1}, \quad (2)$$

where ρ_1 and ρ_2 correspond to atmospherically corrected reflectances of red and near-infrared MODIS bands 1 and 2, respectively. In our case, NDVI is estimated for daylight acquisitions only.

Table 2. Summary of requirements for MODIS products.

Product	Bands required	Parameters required	Re-projection	Resolution (m)	Acquisition, estimated size (MB)
Land mask	Raw data	None	No	250	125
Cloud mask	Raw data	None	No	250	125
Fire mask	Raw data	None	No	250	125
NDVI	1, 2	None	No	250	500
FVC	None	NDVI	No	250	500
Emissivity	1	NDVI, FVC	Only at night	250	500
Water vapour	2, 17, 18, 19	None	Only at night	1000	35
LST	31, 32	Emissivity, water vapour	No	1000	35
SST	31, 32	None	No	1000	35
BRDF	1 to 7	None	Yes	250 to 500	2250
VCI	None	BRDF–NDVI	Yes	250	500

3.2.2. Fraction of vegetation cover

Fraction of vegetation cover (FVC) is estimated from NDVI following Gutman and Ignatov (1998) for daytime acquisitions only as a normalization of NDVI between standard bare soil and dense vegetation values. In the case of MODIS, these values are, respectively, 0.15 and 0.90 (Camacho et al., 2006), and therefore

$$FVC = \frac{(NDVI) - 0.15}{0.90 - 0.15}. \quad (3)$$

3.2.3. Emissivity

Emissivities are estimated for daytime acquisitions from FVC and MODIS band 1 information, following the methodology presented by Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li (2003). These emissivities correspond to MODIS thermal bands 31 and 32 and are estimated differently depending on the vegetation proportion within a given pixel.

In the case of night-time acquisition, this method cannot be implemented due to the lack of solar radiation and therefore the emissivity estimates during the previous day are re-projected to a latitude/longitude grid, averaged, and re-projected back to the night-time acquisition configuration for further calculations.

These emissivities are expressed as average emissivity ε (for bands 31 and 32) and spectral difference of emissivities $\Delta\varepsilon$ for different pixel characteristics:

- Vegetation (NDVI > 0.5):

$$e = 0.99 ; \Delta e = 0. \quad (4)$$

- Mixed pixel ($0.2 \leq NDVI \leq 0.5$):

$$e = 0.971 + 0.018(\text{FVC}); \Delta e = 0.006(1 - (\text{FVC})). \quad (5)$$

- Bare soil (NDVI < 0.2):

$$e = 0.9832 - 0.058\rho_1; \Delta e = 0.0018 - 0.060\rho_1. \quad (6)$$

3.2.4. Water vapour

WV is estimated using the method developed by Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li (2003). This method is based on the attenuation of surface-reflected solar radiation and clouds in near-infrared due to WV absorption. To this end, WV-absorbing bands centred at 0.905, 0.936, and 0.94 μm (bands 17, 18, and 19, respectively), in addition to a WV-transparent band centred at 0.865 μm (band 2), are used as follows:

$$W = 0.192W_{17} + 0.453W_{18} + 0.355W_{19}, \quad (7)$$

where

$$W_{17} = 28.449G_{17}^2 - 54.434G_{17} + 26.314, \quad (8)$$

$$W_{18} = 27.884G_{18}^2 - 23.017G_{18} + 5.012, \quad (9)$$

$$W_{19} = 19.914G_{19}^2 - 26.887G_{19} + 9.446, \quad (10)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} G_{17} &= \frac{L_{17}}{L_2} \\ G_{18} &= \frac{L_{18}}{L_2}, \\ G_{19} &= \frac{L_{19}}{L_2} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where W is atmospheric WV (g cm^{-2}) and L_{17} , L_{18} , L_{19} , and L_2 are at-sensor radiances (RAD-TOA) of MODIS bands 17, 18, 19, and 2, respectively.

In the case of night-time acquisitions, because this method cannot be implemented due to the lack of solar radiation, WV estimates during the previous day are reprojected to a latitude/longitude grid, averaged, and reprojected back to the night-time acquisition configuration for further calculations.

3.2.5. Land surface temperature

LST is estimated for day- and night-time acquisitions using the method developed by Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li (2003):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LST} = & T_{31} + a_1 + a_2(T_{31} - T_{32}) + a_3(T_{31} - T_{32})^2 + (a_4 + a_5W)(1 - \varepsilon) \\ & + (a_6 + a_7W)\Delta\varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where T_{31} and T_{32} are brightness temperatures of MODIS bands 31 and 32, respectively; ε and $\Delta\varepsilon$ are, respectively, the average emissivity and the spectral emissivity difference of these bands; W is the total WV estimated above; and the coefficients $a_1 = 1.02$, $a_2 = 1.79$, $a_3 = 1.20$, $a_4 = 34.83$, $a_5 = -0.68$, $a_6 = -73.27$, and $a_7 = -5.19$ were determined from simulations (details in Sobrino, El Kharraz, and Li 2003).

3.2.6. Sea surface temperature

SST is estimated for day- and night-time acquisitions using the method developed by El Kharraz (2004):

$$\text{SST} = T_{31} + (b_1 + b_2W)(T_{31} - T_{32}) + b_3W + b_4, \quad (13)$$

where T_{31} and T_{32} are brightness temperature of MODIS bands 31 and 32, respectively; W is the total WV estimated above; and the values for b_1 , b_2 , b_3 , and b_4 are respectively 1.90, 0.44, 0.05, and 0.34.

3.3. Advanced products

3.3.1. Bidirectional reflectance distribution function

Standard BRDF methods use reflectance data from MODIS bands 1–7 over 16 days to estimate BRDF model parameters through least-squares optimization. Here, kernel-driven models are used, these being three-parameter semi-empirical linear models. The theoretical basis of these models is that land surface reflectance is modelled as a sum of three kernels representing basic scattering types: isotropic scattering, radiative transfer-type volumetric scattering as from horizontally homogeneous leaf canopies, and geometric–optical surface scattering as from scenes containing three-dimensional objects that cast shadows and are mutually obscured from view at off-nadir angles:

$$\rho(\theta_s, \theta_v, \phi) = k_0 + k_1 F_1(\theta_s, \theta_v, \phi) + k_2 F_2(\theta_s, \theta_v, \phi), \quad (14)$$

where θ_s is the Sun zenith angle; θ_v is the view zenith angle; ϕ is the relative azimuth angle; F_1 and F_2 are the kernels that represent volume scattering and geometric scattering, respectively; and k_0 , k_1 , and k_2 are the model parameters associated with each kernel. F_1 and F_2 are fixed functions of the observation geometry derived from physical considerations of radiative transfer at the surface, while k_0 , k_1 , and k_2 are free parameters estimated on a pixel-by-pixel basis from the data by the least-squares method.

The ‘Ross Thick/Li Sparse reciprocal combination’, hereafter referred as the Ross–Li model, was selected for the processing of MODIS land-surface measurements (Lucht et al. 2000). The volume-scattering kernel (F_1) is based on the Rossthick function derived by Roujean, Leroy, and Deschamps (1992) and modified by Maignan, Bréon, and Lacaze (2004):

$$F_1(\theta_s, \theta_v, \phi) = \frac{4}{3\pi \cos \theta_s + \cos \theta_v} \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \xi \right) \cos \xi + \sin \xi \right] \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\xi}{\xi_0} \right)^{-1} \right) - \frac{1}{3}, \quad (15)$$

where $\cos \xi = \cos \theta_s \cos \theta_v + \sin \theta_s \sin \theta_v \cos \phi$ and ξ_0 is equal to 1.5° .

The geometric kernel (F_2) is based on the LiSparse–Reciprocal model (Li and Strahler 1992) but considering the reciprocal form given by Lucht (1998) that is obtained by the proportions of sunlit and shaded scene components in a scene consisting of randomly located spheroids of height-to-centre-of-crown h and crown vertical to horizontal radius ratio b/r :

$$F_2(\theta_s, \theta_v, \phi) = O(\theta_s', \theta_v', \phi) - \sec \theta_s' - \sec \theta_v' + \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos \xi') \sec \theta_s' \sec \theta_v', \quad (16)$$

where

$$\theta_s' = \arctan\left(\frac{b}{r} \tan \theta_s\right), \text{ idem for } \theta_v', \quad (17)$$

$$\cos \xi' = \cos \theta_s' \cos \theta_v' + \sin \theta_s' \sin \theta_v' \cos \phi, \quad (18)$$

$$O(\theta_s', \theta_v', \phi) = \frac{1}{\pi} (t - \sin t \cos t) (\sec \theta_s' + \sec \theta_v'), \quad (19)$$

where t is defined as

$$\cos t = \min\left(1, \frac{h}{b} \frac{\sqrt{D'^2 + (\tan \theta_s' \tan \theta_v' \sin \phi)^2}}{\sec \theta_s' + \sec \theta_v'}\right) \quad (20)$$

and D' as

$$D' = \sqrt{\tan^2 \theta_s' + \tan^2 \theta_v' - 2 \tan \theta_s' \tan \theta_v' \cos \phi}. \quad (21)$$

The dimensionless crown relative height and shape parameters h/b and b/r are within the kernel and should therefore be preselected. For MODIS processing, $h/b = 2$ and $b/r = 1$ (i.e. the spherical crowns are separated from the ground by half their diameter). Generally, the shape of the crowns affects the BRDF more than their relative height.

This BRDF correction is now being investigated in regard to application to the received MODIS data, as presented above or as proposed by Bréon and Vermote (2012), which expresses the above kernel functions for a whole year as a function of NDVI, and allows for a near-real-time estimation of BRDF-corrected data by using the kernel functions estimated for the previous year.

3.3.2. Vegetation condition index

Similar to FVC, VCI is estimated as a normalization of NDVI between maximum and minimum NDVI values for the considered pixel over a whole year (Kogan 1995):

$$VCI = \frac{(NDVI) - (NDVI)_{\min}}{(NDVI)_{\max} - (NDVI)_{\min}}. \quad (21)$$

Therefore, VCI can only be estimated at the end of each year, although a near-real-time estimation could be obtained from near-real-time BRDF-corrected NDVI, by estimating $(NDVI)_{\min}$ and $(NDVI)_{\max}$ values from the BRDF-corrected NDVI for the previous year.

4. MSG SEVIRI processing

As stated above, both MODIS and MSG SEVIRI streams of data are processed linearly following a similar scheme (see Table 1). The selected algorithms for MSG SEVIRI processing were also chosen from a literature review, and are based on standard procedures (SMAC atmospheric correction; Rahman and Dedieu 1994) using specific methods described below. Characteristics (resolution, average sample size, etc.) of each of the products described below are presented in Table 3.

4.1. Preprocessing

The MSG SEVIRI reception station is equipped with Dartcom software, which allows the acquisition and decoding of the image into level 0 data. Calibration is straightforward, since offset and gain coefficients are included in band metadata. Land/sea mask and observation-viewing zenithal and azimuthal angles are fixed and are available as ancillary files.

Atmospheric correction is then implemented only for pixels under daylight conditions for bands Vis06 and Vis08. To that end, SMAC software (Rahman and Dedieu 1994) was selected and implemented as described in section 3.1, with identical standard values. As in the case of MODIS preprocessing, MSG-SEVIRI WV product is also calculated prior to atmospheric correction.

In regard to thermal channels, the estimation of brightness temperature is required, by inversion of Planck's law (see Equation 1 above).

Table 3. Summary of requirements for MSG SEVIRI products.

Product	Bands required	Parameters required	Frequency	Image, estimated size (MB)
NDVI	Vis06, Vis08	None	15 min, 1 day	26.3
Emissivity	Vis06	NDVI	15 min, 1 day	26.3
Water vapour	Ir108, Ir120	None	15 min	26.3
LST	Ir108, Ir120	Emissivity, water vapour	15 min	26.3
SST	Ir108, Ir120	None	15 min	26.3
BRDF	Vis06, Vis08	None	15 min (1 year)	157.8
VCI	None	BRDF-NDVI	15 min (1 year)	26.3

4.2. Near-real-time products

4.2.1. Normalized difference vegetation index

NDVI is estimated as in Equation (2), but for atmospherically corrected reflectances for MSG SEVIRI bands Vis08 (near-infrared) and Vis06 (red), respectively.

However, NDVI is not expected to change over 24 hours. Therefore, all 15-min NDVI estimates should not vary if not due to changes in the atmosphere (cloud cover) or illumination geometry (since MSG observation geometry is fixed). This property can be used to retrieve BRDF properties.

4.2.2. Emissivity

Emissivities are estimated for daytime acquisitions from NDVI and Vis06 band information, following the threshold method. These emissivities correspond to MSG thermal bands Ir108 and Ir120 and are estimated differently depending on the vegetation proportion within a given pixel.

In the case of night-time acquisition, this method cannot be implemented due to the lack of solar radiation and therefore the emissivity estimates during the previous day are used.

These emissivities are expressed as ε_{108} and ε_{120} for different pixel characteristics:

- Vegetation (NDVI > 0.5):

$$\varepsilon_{108} = 0.99; \varepsilon_{120} = 0.99. \quad (22)$$

- Mixed pixel ($0.2 \leq \text{NDVI} \leq 0.5$):

$$\varepsilon_{108} = 0.968 + 0.021(\text{PV}); \varepsilon_{120} = 0.976 + 0.015(\text{PV}). \quad (23)$$

- Bare soil (NDVI < 0.2):

$$\varepsilon_{108} = 0.977 - 0.048\rho_{\text{Vis06}}; \varepsilon_{120} = 0.981 - 0.026\rho_{\text{Vis06}}. \quad (24)$$

where ρ_{band} is the atmospherically corrected reflectance for MSG SEVIRI bands (bands = Vis06, Vis08) and PV is the proportion of vegetation within the pixel, estimated as

$$\text{PV} = \frac{((\text{NDVI}) - 0.2)^2}{0.09}. \quad (25)$$

4.2.3. Water vapour

A first approach for estimating WV was based on the method developed by Sobrino and Romaguera (2008). However, due to the complex application of this algorithm to near-real-time processing, a novel instantaneous approach was designed (Julien et al. 2015) and is presented briefly below:

$$W = w_0 + w_1 T_{062}(T_{108} - T_{120}), \quad (26)$$

where T_{108} and T_{120} are brightness temperatures of MSG bands Ir108 and Ir120, respectively, and T_{062} is the brightness temperature of the MSG SEVIRI water absorption band at $6.2 \mu\text{m}$ (Wv062). Values for coefficients w_0 and w_1 are, respectively, 1.4 g cm^{-2} and $0.00692 \text{ g cm}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

4.2.4. Land surface temperature

LST is estimated for day- and night-time acquisitions using the method developed by Atitar and Sobrino (2009):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LST} = & T_{108} + \left[1.34 - \frac{0.11}{\cos^2\theta} \right] (T_{108} - T_{120}) + \left[0.29 + \frac{0.08}{\cos^2\theta} \right] (T_{108} - T_{120})^2 \\ & + \left[60.67 - \frac{10.01}{\cos^2\theta} \right] (1 - \varepsilon) + \left[-6.71 + \frac{2.47}{\cos^2\theta} \right] W(1 - \varepsilon) \quad , \quad (27) \\ & + \left[-125.91 + \frac{15.09}{\cos^2\theta} \right] \Delta\varepsilon + \left[19.44 - \frac{4.27}{\cos^2\theta} \right] W\Delta\varepsilon + \left[-0.44 + \frac{0.57}{\cos^2\theta} \right] \end{aligned}$$

where T_{108} and T_{120} are brightness temperatures of MSG bands Ir108 and Ir120, respectively; ε and $\Delta\varepsilon$ are, respectively, the average emissivity and the spectral emissivity difference of these bands; W is the total WV estimated above; and θ is the observation zenith angle.

4.2.5. SST

SST is estimated for day- and night-time acquisitions using the method developed by Romaguera, Sobrino, and Olesen (2006):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SST} = & T_{108} + (0.99 \cos \theta + 0.21)(T_{108} - T_{120}) \\ & + \left(\frac{0.364}{\cos \theta} + 0.15 \right) (T_{108} - T_{120})^2 + \frac{0.327}{\cos^2\theta} + 0.11 \quad , \quad (28) \end{aligned}$$

where T_{108} and T_{120} are brightness temperatures of MSG bands Ir108 and Ir120, respectively, and θ is the observation zenith angle.

4.3. Advanced products

4.3.1. Bidirectional reflectance distribution function

The approach for BRDF-corrected MSG SEVIRI data (Vis06 and Vis08) is the same as that for MODIS data (see above), and is currently being implemented. However, in the case of MSG data, since the observation angle is fixed by the geostationary characteristic of its associated platform, only the normalization of illumination can be carried out directly from MSG data. Approaches exist to normalize observations to illumination and observation nadir, although additional data are needed (e.g. from MODIS sensor). Here we prefer MSG-only processing, since it is easier to implement and does not hinder the time-series analysis of MSG data, because the observations will be normalized to a

standard observation and illumination geometry, consisting of the observation angle for each pixel and nadir illumination. Therefore, the BRDF correction will only consider differences in pixel illumination.

4.3.2. *Vegetation condition index*

MSG SEVIRI VCI is estimated following the same approach as described above for MODIS VCI. NDVI minimum and maximum values are estimated after time-series reconstruction using the iterative interpolation for data reconstruction (IDR) approach (Julien and Sobrino 2010) as implemented in Sobrino, Julien, and Soria (2013) for the previous year, and estimated immediately after image reception, screening out values for which the NDVI increase over the previous 24 hours is within a pixel-specific threshold as determined from NDVI temporal behaviour analysis for the previous year. Therefore, the VCI-estimated data are incremental, updated at each image acquisition for cloud-free pixels.

5. Applications

With the availability of such a huge amount of data, countless applications can be carried out, from vegetation monitoring and forecasting to disaster early-warning. Hereafter, we present two among these applications, focused on the one hand on hot spot detection and on the other hand on phenology monitoring. Finally, the geo-portal for the download of the products presented above is briefly presented.

5.1 *Hot spot detection*

Forest fires are a considerable danger to human health, through corporal and property damage as well as air contamination, and play a key role in the carbon cycle through the emission of CO₂, a gas which has been evidenced as a major contributor to global warming. As regards spectral information, forest fires (and fires in general) present temperatures in the mid-wave infrared (MIR) and thermal infrared (TIR) region higher than their surroundings, which allows for their detection from remote sensors such as MODIS (Giglio et al. 2003) and MSG SEVIRI (Calle, Casanova, and Romo 2006). In Table 4, we present a sample of four hot spots detected in Portugal from MSG SEVIRI acquisition on 2 September 2014 at 17:45 (UTC), along with the estimated characteristics of the detected fire (fire radiative power (FRP), fire temperature, and burning area). The system is configured so that alert emails are sent to warn of forest fires in southwestern Europe as soon as they are detected (within 5 min of the end of image reception) from either MSG SEVIRI or MODIS instruments.

Table 4. Coordinates and characteristics of the fire detected from MSG SEVIRI acquisition on 2 September 2014 at 17:45 (UTC).

Pixel	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Fire radiative power (MW)	Temperature (K)	Area (ha)
1	40.69	-6.89	19.7	1194	0.24
2	40.69	-6.85	28.5	932	0.87
3	40.25	-7.73	34.1	1495	0.22
4	40.25	-7.69	32.0	1857	0.12

Figure 2. End of season (EOS) dates for 2013 as retrieved from MSG SEVIRI NDVI time series.

5.2 Phenology estimation

Monitoring NDVI throughout a complete year allows for the estimation of phenological phases, such as the dates corresponding to the start and end of the season (SOS and EOS, respectively). This information is of utmost importance since both dates play a role in water and carbon cycles, in direct relation to climate warming prediction, and are a known indicator of climate change through plant sensitivity to temperatures. In [Figure 2](#) we present an example of EOS dates for 2013 for the entire MSG SEVIRI disc. To that end, instantaneous NDVI values at 12:00 UTC have been cloud-corrected and gap-filled through the procedure described in [Sobrino, Julien, and Soria \(2013\)](#) and then analysed for yearly cycle characterization. Direct comparison to independent PEP725 ground station data showed an error below 1 week for EOS in Europe ([Sobrino, Julien, and Soria 2013](#)).

5.3 Geo-portal

All products shown in bold in [Table 1](#) are available for download for registered users (registration upon request) from the geo-portal located at <http://ceosspain.lpi.uv.es>. Guest users can browse the available data, although without permission to download. The architecture of the geo-portal is described thoroughly in [Sevilla et al. \(2015\)](#), and allows for the search of the entire database (since mid-2007) for user-defined specific locations and acceptable cloud contamination levels in the case of MODIS data, while MSG SEVIRI data are provided for the entire observation disc only. This geo-portal is presented in [Figure 3](#).

Figure 3. Overview of the geo-portal from which all MODIS and SEVIRI products since 2007 can be downloaded (<http://ceospain.lpi.uv.es>). Red rectangle corresponds to the area selected (Iberian Peninsula) for database exploration.

6. Conclusion

The MODIS and MSG SEVIRI receiving stations at the Global Change Unit of the University of Valencia have been operational since mid-2007. All received data were processed as described above, allowing for specific applications such as fire hot spot detection, phenology monitoring, and temperature spatial homogeneity studies (not described here). These data are available for download to the scientific community and the general public from the geo-portal on the CEOS-SPAIN webpage: <http://ceospain.lpi.uv.es>. Additional products (BRDF correction) will be added in the near future, and products presented will be validated from multitemporal data recorded at various ground stations in Spain, representative of various land covers and land uses. Finally, the available parameters will be extended to the Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite instrument, from which data are already being received at our station.

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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